

External factors affecting perceived usability: A closer look at the effect of emotion prior to interaction

Maria Angelica Velazquez* Frank E. Ritter **

** The Pennsylvania State University, Industrial and Manufacturing Engineering Department
University Park, United States, mav189@psu.edu*

*** The Pennsylvania State University, Department of Information, Science and Technology Studies
University Park, United States, frank.ritter@psu.edu*

Abstract: Usability is the extent to which a product is effective, efficient, and satisfying in a particular context. Usability assessment can be important for the development of successful products as it evaluates the way the products satisfy the user needs. As emotions are part of cognition, it is reasonable to think they may influence the human interaction with products, affecting the perceived usability. Based on this premise, multiple researchers have proposed models for product appraisal considering objective usability in terms of effectiveness and efficiency and subjective aspects such as the emotion involved. However, these approaches do not include external factors such as skill level, individual preferences and affective states; yet, these external factors may affect the perception of usability. This research work explores the effects of external factors in the perceived usability of products, and specifically focuses on the effect of emotions experienced just before interaction with a product. Data from a preliminary study on the effect of emotional states in perceived usability is presented. The results showed that when positive emotion exists, the perceived usability is significantly higher than the one perceived in the presence of negative emotion.

Key words: Usability, emotions, product appraisal

1. Introduction

Usability studies the extent to which products and systems are functional and practical to the user in meeting their needs. Originally, usability was developed as a way to assess and monitor employees' productivity in the workplace. Nowadays, it has been extended to evaluate the degree to which products and services of any kind are able to suffice the user needs and to evaluate the human-product relationship. With the advancement of new technologies, the concept of usability has been enriched by knowledge in human development and cognitive processes, incorporating empirical data on challenges experienced by users [1], and providing a variety of approaches and metrics for usability assessments.

While several usability models have been proposed, the potential effects due to individual factors such as culture, skills and affective states on the perception of usability have only been rarely studied. These effects might seem obvious, yet there is very limited evidence on the extent to which perceived usability is affected by these factors,

which makes it difficult to account and design for.

This research examines the effects of affective or emotional states on the perception of product usability. Although we readily acknowledge the effects of other factors such as gender, culture and skills, we are mainly interested in the emotional aspect as there is a void in the literature in this regard. Further, there is an emerging interest in emotional design and usability, which makes the study of emotional states a research priority. Thus, this article focuses on emotions and their effects during interaction of the human with a product, and hence the perception on the usability.

Emotions are an important element of human life. Emotions have been recently acknowledged in the human factors field as powerful motivators that may influence perception, cognition and creativity [2], and as part of human cognition, behavior, values, judgment, and agency [3]. Researchers have suggested that when a person interacts with a product, the emotions experienced may impact such interactions, and consequently, the way the product is perceived [2, 4-13]. Fields of Human Factors and Human-Computer Interaction are increasingly incorporating aesthetics, hedonic quality and emotions as part of product evaluations as a response to the traditional usability methods' portrayal of the human as merely a cognitive and information processor [14].

The importance of emotions and pleasure in the human-product interaction has been highlighted before. For example, recognizing the limitations of traditional usability in the study of the emotions and the product experience, Dormann introduced "emotional usability" as *the degree to which a product is desirable or serves a need beyond traditional functional objectives* [15]. For the most part, however, researchers focused on the emotions generated while interacting with the product and not what emotion the human has right before his/her interaction with the product. In other words, the potential effects of human affective states right before product interaction are mostly neglected. This neglected piece is the focus of the research here. Given the new trends in emotional design, there is a need for designers and usability practitioners to know the ways in which emotional states affect the way emotions are evoked during interactions with products.

We conducted a study in which the effects of affective states in perceived usability were tested. The participants were induced with positive and negative affective states, and consecutively they were asked to interact with a smart phone and software, and then rate the usability of the product at the end of their interaction. In the following sections of the paper, we first provide a review of the related literature, and then provide details of the experimental design. Results and conclusions complete the paper.

2. Emotion, cognition and usability

Emotions, inherent to human life, are mental and physiological states associated with a variety of feelings, thoughts, and behavior, experienced subjectively by individuals. Early researchers visualized emotions as mental states that interfere with rational thinking and cognitive activities, arguing a separation between rational and emotional behavior. For many years, the literature agreed in the non-logical nature of emotions, and disregarded its importance in rational and cognitive processes, implying that acting emotionally meant acting irrationally, with poor judgment [2]. This stigmatic view of emotions as non-rational agents has dominated thinking until recently [16].

Over the past 30 years researchers have become more interested in studying the interaction of emotions and cognition and their influence on rationality and human performance. This research demonstrated the effects of emotion on memory, human performance, learning, perception of ambiguous stimuli and of the likelihood of events [17], and suggested that emotions can be helpful and important for effective human thinking, problem solving, behavior, decision making and many other cognitive processes [2, 11, 18-20]. Accordingly, today emotions are considered important in human intelligence, rational decision making, social interaction, perception, memory, learning and creativity. They are helpful for the execution of intelligent day-to-day performance [2] and therefore, they may affect multiple aspects of human's life.

Multiple researchers have demonstrated that emotions play an important role in human activities and decision making, potentially influencing mechanisms of rational thinking [2]. Damasio's experiments showed that neurological, hormonal and physiological processes operate simultaneously in a structured architecture, generating cognitive and affective mechanisms important for human thought, judgment, creativity, feelings, actions, and decision making. The relevance of emotions in cognition was also described by Simon [19] in his theory of information processing, which suggests that emotions are helpful to human's thinking and problem solving activities and present them as interruption mechanisms that allow the processing system to respond to urgent needs. Other researchers such as Norman described emotions as an important part of life that affects the way the human feels, behaves, and thinks. Therefore, emotions may be regarded as an significant form of cognition [11].

These studies provide evidence for the effects of emotional states in multiple cognitive activities and provide the basis to understand the mechanisms involved. Even though the effects of emotional states in product appraisal have been studied, most of these studies are based on psychology and thus, do not provide practical knowledge to the product development community. Our research intends to study such effects specifically on perceived usability, which is the standard use in product development to validate the usefulness of a product. To the best of our knowledge, such effects have never been analyzed from the usability perspective, and thus, had been overlooked to a great extent by the human-computer interaction and usability community. Models of product acceptance have proven that utility and usefulness, which are basic pillars of usability, are crucial factors of product acceptance. Thus, it becomes important to understand to which extend the affective state of the user would affect his/her perception of usability, and hence, product acceptance and usage.

2.1 Usability

Usability is the extent to which the product meets the user needs. ISO 9241-11 defines usability as the extent to which a product is effective, efficient, and satisfying in a particular context of use. Usability assessments are important for the development of successful and satisfying products as they evaluate the human-product relationship, and the way the products satisfy the user needs in terms of efficiency, effectiveness and satisfaction. Usability assessments are helpful to assess and reduce product risks.

In general, if the product or service assists the user to achieve a goal, which can be done comfortably and within the cognitive and physical capabilities, the product or service can be said to fit the user [21]. This approach visualizes the human as the "user", characterized by cognitive and physical components, and the product as tools,

conceptualizing the human-product interaction as making use of a tool to accomplish a task [21]. This limited view ignores aspects of the human such as their hopes, fears, feelings, dreams, and many aspects associated with the emotional aspects of the product experience. Discerning the effects of emotions in cognitive activities is important to integrate emotional responses of the user in usability assessments. Usability, without considering emotional aspects, is providing a limited view of the user experience with the product and the use context.

2.2 Models of usability

Shackel’s model of usability [22] was among the first ones to recognize the relativity of the concept, describing usability as a dimension of product acceptance along with utility, likeability, and costs. Figure 1 show the relation of usability within the acceptance model and provides the usability dimensions of usability as described by Shackel.

Figure 1: Model of product acceptance by Shackel [22].

Within the context of product acceptance, usability is defined as “the capability to be used by humans easily and effectively” [22]. It is composed of subjective perception of product and objective measures of the human-product interaction [23]. Here, effectiveness refers to the speed and errors when interacting with the system or product, learnability is the relation of performance to training and frequency of use, flexibility is the degree in which adaptation to other environments is allowed, and attitude refers to the level of acceptance in terms of tiredness, discomfort, frustration and personal effort [23].

Similarly, Nielsen defined usability as an aspect of product acceptance, suggesting that usability and utility influence the product usefulness. Utility refers to the capacity of the product functions to help users execute tasks while usability refers to the way users make use of the product. In Nielsen’s model of acceptability, the product usefulness affects the practical aspects of product acceptability. Figure 2 shows a diagram of Nielsen’s acceptability model.

Figure 2: Model of product acceptance by Nielsen (1993) [24].

ISO 9241 part 11 describes usability as quality of use, which is composed of product attributes and user-product

relationship within context. The three dimensions of usability are effectiveness (accuracy and completeness of goals), efficiency (expenditure of resources), and satisfaction (comfort and acceptance of use). Figure 3 is a diagram of ISO 9241 usability model.

Figure 3: ISO 9241 usability model [25].

From the perspective of the user experience with the product, Bevan [26] provides a definition of usability in terms of “quality of use”, which is defined as “the extent to which a product satisfies stated and implied needs when used under stated conditions” [26]. In his definition Bevan argues that quality in use can be used to measure usability by measuring the extent to which specific goals may be accomplished with effectiveness, efficiency and satisfaction by specific users performing specific tasks in specified environments. Considering the purpose with which products are created, to help the user achieve a goal, Bevan states that quality of use is the right measurement to product usability, as it will capture the degree of meeting the user requirements by being effective, efficient in use of resources, and satisfying to the user.

The usability model presented by Keinonen [22] is based on a differentiation of product types, providing different usability criteria for automatic products and interactive products. In the model, the usability criteria consist of: utility, referring to the product’s ability to help in the completion of a goal; capacity, which is the extent to which the product output is sufficient to the product’s purpose; subjective pleasure, which is related to the feelings of the user towards the product; reliability, referring to the rate of faults in the product; easiness to learn, easiness to remember and error rate.

Most of the usability models agree on the inclusion of dimensions such as easiness to use, easiness to learn, effectiveness, efficiency, user satisfaction or user attitude towards the product or the system. ISO’s definition of usability focuses on the quality of work and the product, providing a less user-centered view of usability when compared to Shackel and Nielsen’s view [22, 24], which consider usability as an important dimension of product acceptance. In fact, both Shackel and Nielsen’s usability models emphasize the fact that usability is a determinant factor of product acceptance. However, none of these models emphasize the relevance of individual differences in the perception of usability.

3. A closer look to the effect of emotion in usability

The effect of affective states in the generation of evaluative judgment has been previously studied. Mood has been shown to affect consumer behavior in many ways. Research in advertising, perceived risk, and new product evaluation supports the idea that negative or positive affect can color unrelated consumer judgments, such as evaluations of brand extensions and actual choices [27-29]. Even moods have been suggested to be sources of

information in evaluative judgment of products and choices [30]. In general, it is thought that positive affect promotes behavior while negative inhibits behavior [31].

However, these studies focus on the general perception of products and the circumstances in which the products are accepted by the users. Thus, they provide insights from the consumer research and marketing perspectives. Such perspectives focus mostly on product attractiveness and attachment, which many times neglect the usability evaluation of products. It is common practice to rely on human factors and human-computer interaction disciplines to assess the usability of products.

Usability is a very important part of new product evaluation. Although the effects of emotions in new product development have been studied, the effects on the perceived usability of emotions have not been assessed. Based on the supporting evidence of the effects of affective states in new product evaluation, we believe that a possible explanation of such effects is the effect of affective states in the perceived usability.

4. Methodology

This study explores the carry over effects of emotions experienced just prior to interacting with a product, and their effects on the perceived product usability. In this experiment, positive and negative emotions were elicited to the participant right before their interaction with a smart phone. They were asked to assess the usability of the smart phone based on their interaction.

The experiment was divided in two sessions, seven days apart. A different emotion was elicited to the participants (positive or negative) in each session. The seven days separation was to allow sufficient forgetting of the tasks and the emotion experienced. The participants were randomly assigned to a specific sequence of emotions experiences (e.g., positive in first session, negative in second session). The effect of emotion in perceived usability was assessed by comparing the usability scores for the positive and the negative affect conditions. Figure 4 shows the sequence of the tasks executed by the participants.

Figure 4: Task Sequence for Experiment

4.1 Subjects

The participants were recruited from the Industrial Engineering department. A total of 27 participants took place in this study. The sample consisted of 13 females and 14 males, with average age of 21.2 years (20-24 range), all industrial engineering students. They had either junior or senior standing.

4.2 Materials

A portable computer with Windows Vista Home Edition was used to execute the computer tasks. Director MX was used to program the interface for the computer task. A smart phone from the brand HTC (HTC Pure) was also used, with the Windows Mobile 6.0 operating system. A software program for personal finance management was used. To measure the elicited emotions, the Positive and Negative Affect Schedule (PANAS) [32] was used.

4.3 Experimental design

A single-factor repeated measures experiment was conducted. The factor controlled was the type of emotion, and it had two levels, positive and negative. Each participant was exposed to each level of the emotional state in separate sessions.

4.4 Procedure

The participants came to the experimentation room and were briefed on the requirements of the study. A pre-experiment questionnaire was provided to the subjects to obtain information about their background, interest, and previous experience with similar phones and software. Then, they were asked to complete the PANAS questionnaire to set the baseline of the emotional state of the subject. Immediately after, the subjects were allowed to interact with the smart phone-software system for about 5 minutes.

For the purpose of emotion induction, the participants were asked to execute a computer task that served as the mean to elicit both positive and negative emotions. Right after, the participants were asked to report their level of emotion in the PANAS questionnaire, and to execute a series of tasks in the software using the smart phone provided for about 10 minutes. After their interaction, they completed the System Usability Scale (SUS) and the IBM System Usability Questionnaire to assess the usability of the cell phone and the software.

In the second session, which is executed seven days later, the participants experienced the emotion that was not elicited during the first session, and the remaining data collection was done. The participants completed a post-experiment questionnaire and were informed of the true purpose of the experiment at the end of the second session.

5. Results

All the participants were able to complete the two sessions. The effectiveness of the emotion manipulations were tested by comparing the pre-experiment affective score with the post-computer task affective score reported in PANAS. The differences in pre and post manipulation scores were statistically significant for positive and negative emotion ($P < 0.05$).

The usability of the smart phone was assessed by completing the IBM Usability Questionnaire and the System Usability Scale (SUS). In both questionnaires the usability score represented the participant's perceived level of usability. Table 1 shows the mean usability index reported in SUS and IBM questionnaires for the positive and negative emotion sessions. In both questionnaires the mean usability score assigned to the smart phone in the positive affect condition was higher than the mean score in the negative affect condition.

Table 1: Mean values for SUS and IBM usability index for positive and negative emotion.

	Mean Usability	
	SUS	IBM
Positive emotion	65.65	3.90
Negative emotion	52.96	3.26

We are interested in knowing if there is a significant difference in the perceived usability between the positive and negative affect conditions. For that purpose the following hypothesis is formulated.

Ho: The mean difference in perceived usability score for the system in the presence of positive affect is equal to the mean difference in usability score for the system in the presence of negative affect.

An analysis of variance was done to test the significance of the emotion in the usability responses. Other factors such as the session and the sequence in which the stimuli were observed were analyzed as well. Individual analyses of variance were done for each response of each usability assessment method (SUS, IBM). Table 2 summarizes the results of the analysis of variance for each measurement method.

Table 2: ANOVA results for Experiment.

Factor	Statistic	Method	
		SUS	IBM
Emotion	F (1,53)	6.04	4.32
	P-value	.017	.043
Emotion Sequence	F (1,53)	1.61	0.56
	P-value	.210	.458
Session	F (1,53)	0.05	2.84
	P-value	.831	.098

At 95% confidence, the factor representing the emotional state was significant for both methods. Therefore, we may reject the null hypothesis. This implies a difference in perceived usability based on the emotional state in which the user is. As shown in table 1, the mean usability scores obtained for both methods was lower in the negative emotion condition compared to the score in the positive emotion.

Other factors such as the emotion sequence (e.g., positive emotion in the first session, negative in the second session) and the session were not significant. This implies that the changes in usability were not due to the order in which the emotions were experienced, or the session in which the system were assessed.

The statistical power for the SUS method to detect a maximum difference of 14 was equal to 76%. For the IBM questionnaire the power to detect a maximum difference of 0.9 was equal to 79.8%.

4. Conclusions and Future Work

Usability is an ever-expanding concept that continues to evolve along with the knowledge about design considerations and human-product interaction in various contexts [1]. Traditionally, the field of usability has focused on ease of use and functionality, which is assessed by measurable, observable cognitive activity. *Nowadays emotion and pleasure engineering is becoming more important, as pleasurable products are becoming more of a competitive differentiator in the product market* [33].

While the emotional and affective aspects of the product experience are acknowledged, they have been studied in isolation from traditional usability. Moreover the effect of individual factors such as cultural differences, skills and affective state upon interaction with products is seldom assessed.

In this article we argue for the need of more research in these areas. We started by investigating the effects of emotion in the perceived usability. Our experiment showed that there is a relationship between perceived usability and the emotion experienced upon interaction with products. When positive emotion exists, the perceived usability is significantly higher than the one perceived in the presence of negative emotions. The results of this research will support designer's efforts for emotional robust designs. Thus, no matter what the emotional state of the user is, the affective state that is required to assure quality of performance and optimizing product usage will be assured.

There is a range of products for which the user's affective state should be controlled. For example, software systems used in emergency response, airplane cockpits and air traffic control need to be designed to minimize anxiety, stress, frustration, and support timely and accurate decision making of the user. Also, many products are designed to generate a determined emotional state based on the product characteristics and the context in which the interface is to be used. In such cases the effectiveness of the designs to support the desired emotional state is not tested for the range of emotions that may be present prior the interaction with the product. Thus, there is a risk that existing moods or emotional states alter the emotions generated during the interaction.

Moreover, if the task to be executed in the interface would generate emotions, the designers should be aware of possible carry-over of previous emotions. These carry-over effects may lower the thresholds of emotions and propitiate the generation of new and augmented states. These new emotions may affect the performance of the user and the perception of the product. Although smart phones and their software may not represent environments with constant stress and cognitive workload we believe they are appropriate to establish the baseline of the effect of emotions in usability.

This would help designers to create products that are able to overcome negative emotions and elicit positive

affects that improve the user's quality of life. Designers cannot control user's moods as variables, thus they need to be aware of these effects, and produce robust designs capable of overcoming such effects. It is expected that designers would want a happy and satisfied user who will likely keep using and recommend the product to others.

The findings of this study have implications for marketing practitioners as well. Often, they attempt to manipulate affective states by for example, placing their advertising after a humorous television program or endeavoring to create uplifting ads [30]. But how effective these techniques are in the presence of pre-conceived positive or negative emotional states? The answer to this question is unknown.

In the same fashion, we encourage investigators to study the effects of individual factors such as gender and personality type in perceived usability. Additionally, further research needs to be done to understand the ways in which emotion upon interaction with products may affect its perception, and the generation of new emotions while interacting with the product.

5. References

1. Carroll, J.M. and H.M. Mentis, *The useful interface experience: the role and transformation of usability*, in *Product Experience*, H.N.J. Schifferstein and P. Hekkerd, Editors. 2008, Elsevier: San Diego, CA
2. Picard, R., *Affective Computing*, ed. T.M. Press. 1997, Cambridge, Massachusetts The MIT Press. 292.
3. Love, T., *Beyond emotions in designing and designs: epistemological and practical issues* in *Design and Emotion* D. McDonagh, et al., Editors. 2002, Taylor & Francis New York p. 387-391.
4. Brave, S. and C. Nass, *Emotion in Human-Computer Interaction*, in *The human-computer interaction handbook: fundamentals, evolving technologies and emerging applications*, A.J. Julie and S. Andrew, Editors. 2003, L. Erlbaum Associates Inc. p. 1242.
5. Desmet, P., R. Porcelijn, and M.B. van Dijk, *Emotional design; Application of a research-based design approach*. Knowledge, Technology and Policy, 2007. **20**(3): p. 14.
6. Dillon, A., *Beyond usability: process, outcome and affect in human-computer interactions*. Canadian Journal of Library and Information Science 2002. **26**(4): p. 12.
7. Green, W.S. and P.W. Jordan, *Pleasure with Products: Beyond Usability* 2002, New York Taylor & Francis.
8. Helander, M. and M. Tham, *Hedonomics - Affective human factors design*. Ergonomics, 2003. **46**: p. 1269-1272.
9. Jordan, P.W., *Designing Pleasurable Products: An Introduction to the New Human Factors*. 2000, Philadelphia, PA: Taylor and Francis.
10. Mahlke, S., *Aesthetic and Symbolic Qualities as Antecedents of Overall Judgements of Interactive Products*, in *People and Computers XX — Engage Proceedings of HCI 2006* N. Bryan-Kinns, et al., Editors. 2007, Springer London. p. 57-64.
11. Norman, D.A., *Emotional Design: Why we love or hate everyday things*. 2004, New York Basic Books.
12. Tractinsky, N., A.S. Katz, and D. Ikar, *What is beautiful is usable*. Interacting with Computers, 2000. **13**(2): p. 127-145.
13. Zhang, P. and N. Li, *The importance of affective quality*. Commun. ACM, 2005. **48**(9): p. 105-108.
14. Green, W.S. and P.W. Jordan, *Human Factors in Product Design: Current Practice and Future Trends*. 1999, Philadelphia: Taylor and Francis.
15. Dormann, C., *Affective Experiences in the Home: Measuring Emotions*, in *Proceedings of HOIT '03*. 2003: Irvine, California.
16. Dalglish, T. and M.J. Power, *Handbook of Emotion and Cognition* 1999, New York: John Wiley & Sons.

17. Eich, E., et al., *Cognition and Emotion*. Cognition, memory and language, ed. C. Points. 2000, New York: Oxford University Press.
18. Simon, H.A., *Motivational and emotional controls of cognition*. Psychological review, 1967. **74**(1): p. 29-39.
19. Damasio, A.R., *Descartes' error: emotion, reason, and the human brain*. 1994, New York Avon Books.
20. Power, M. and T. Dalgleish, *Cognition and emotion: from order to disorder*. Second Edition ed. 2008, New York: Psychology Press.
21. Blythe, M.A., *Funology: from usability to enjoyment* Human-computer interaction series Vol. 3. 2003, Boston, MA: Kluwer Academic Publishers. 293.
22. Shackel, B., *Usability - context, framework, definition, design and evaluation*, in *Human factors for informatics usability*. 1991, Cambridge University Press. p. 21-37.
23. Keinonen, T., *Theory of a design goal: Usability of interactive products*, in *Arteology, or the study of professional skills*, P. Routio, Editor. 2007.
24. Nielsen, J., *Usability Engineering* 1993, Boston, MA: Academic Press Inc.
25. ISO, *ISO 9241-11: Ergonomic requirements for office work with visual display terminals (VDTs)*, in *Part 11: Guidance on usability*. 1998, International Organisation for Standardisation.
26. Bevan, N., *Measuring usability as quality of use*. Software Quality Journal, 1995. **4**: p. 115-150.
27. Fedorikhin, A. and C.A. Cole, *Mood Effects on Attitudes, Perceived Risk and Choice: Moderators and Mediators*. Journal of Consumer Psychology, 2004. **14**(1-2): p. 2-12.
28. Gorn, G.J., M.E. Goldberg, and K. Basu, *Mood, Awareness, and Product Evaluation*. Journal of Consumer Psychology, 1993. **2**(3): p. 237-256.
29. Chaudhuri, A., *Risk*, in *Emotion and Reason in Consumer Behavior*, A. Chaudhuri, Editor. 1990, Elsevier Burlington, MA.
30. White, K. and C. McFarland, *When are moods most likely to influence consumers' product preferences? The role of mood focus and perceived relevance of moods*. Journal of Consumer Psychology, 2009. **19**(3): p. 526-536.
31. Clore, G.L. and J.R. Hudtsinger, *How Emotions Inform Judgment and Regulate Thought*. TRENDS in Cognitive Sciences 2007. **11**(9): p. 7.
32. Watson, D., L.A. Clark, and A. Tellegen, *Development and validation of brief measures of positive and negative affect: The PANAS scales*. Journal of personality and social psychology, 1988. **54**(6): p. 1063-1070.
33. Spillers, F. (2008) *Emotion as a Cognitive Artifact and the Design Implications for Products That are Perceived As Pleasurable*.